

Understanding Issues Associated with Using Fiber Length SMC Recyclate in Bulk Molding Compounds with the Aim of Improving their Strengths

Rebecca DeRosa, Eric Telfeyan, Gabrielle Gaustad and Steve Mayes
New York State College of Ceramics at Alfred University

Abstract

The vast majority of composites materials are non-biodegradable so the annual cost of disposal is on the order of hundreds of millions of dollars. Thermoset matrix composites make up a large portion of the non-biodegradable waste. The greatest portions of thermoset waste are sheet molding (SMC) and bulk molding compounds (BMC). Regrinding is currently the most widely used recycling process for SMC. It has been well documented that when recycled (SMC) fibers are used to partially replace virgin reinforcement in BMCs the strength of the resulting composite can be decreased by 30% or more. Although the decrease has been well demonstrated, little investigation has been made into the causes for the reduction. In this investigation reground polyester matrix glass fiber SMC from Mecerlec Recycling was used as replacement for virgin glass fiber in polyester matrix BMCs. Visual inspection, microscopy, and Fourier infrared transform spectroscopy (FTIR) were used to analyze the fracture surface of the recyclate. Analysis showed a significant portion of the recyclate consists of chips with resin and CaCO_3 and little glass fiber at the fracture surface.

The strength of the BMCs was determined using 3-point flexural tests. Scanning electron and optical microscopy were used to analyze the fracture of the BMC samples. BMC having a 1 to 1 replacement of recycled SMC for virgin fiber had a 68% reduction in strength. Microscopic analysis of the fracture surface revealed poor bonding between the recycled matrix material and the new matrix. The bonding problem was particularly bad for recyclate from SMC containing thermoplastic cure shrinkage additives. Poor bonding between the recycled material and the new matrix is one of the major causes for the low strength of BMC containing recyclate.

To improve the strength the BMC two recyclate surface modification approaches were investigated. One based on plasma treatment and another based on introducing unsaturation to the polyester chains on the surface of the recyclate. Oxygen Plasma is used to clean and create reactive groups such as COH, COOH, and OH on the surface of the recyclate. The groups are likely to react with the components of the new resin improving bonding. Introduction of unsaturation into polyester chains on the surface creates sites for covalent bonding of the recyclate to the new resin chains via the styrene crosslinker. The goal is to improve polymer-polymer interfacial strength of recycled BMC via covalent bonding between the recyclate and virgin resin.

Key Terms: Recycling Composites, Sheet Molding Compounds, Bulk Molding Compounds, Recycled SMC, BMC Strength Properties, and Automotive Composites

Introduction

Estimates from the Composite Fabricators Association indicate that 3.9 billion pounds of composite materials were shipped in 2000¹. The amount of composites shipped has increased steadily since the early 1990s when it was approximately 2.2 billion pounds². A variety of industries including electronics, automotive, and transportation have contributed significantly to the increase. For example the automotive industry has been steadily increasing its use of composite materials to produce lighter more fuel-efficient cars. Composites such as sheet molding compounds (SMC) and bulk molding compounds (BMC) are two such composites typically used because of their high strength to weight ratio and environmental resistance. Since the 1980s the housing for car headlamps have been produced using BMCs³. More recently the Ford Motor Company has introduced a SMC muffler heat shield shaving 5.5

pounds off their Explorer model⁴. Daimler-Chrysler's 2.7L-V6 engines have been outfitted with BMC vinyl ester composite valve covers, which significantly reduced weight over the metal covers³. In fact, of the composites in cars in 1994, 56% of them consisted of thermoset composites and of the composites in cars 56% of them fall under the category of SMC and BMC². SMC and BMC are also used extensively in the electronics, home appliance, and transportation industries. Though a variety of thermoset composites exist, many of which are of the low production volume high tech sort used in the aerospace industry, because of their use in high volume applications, SMC and BMC makeup the largest portion of thermoset composite waste. In 1995 it was estimated that 200 million pounds of SMC was used by the auto industry alone and in 2001 estimates indicate that 500 million pounds of BMC was used worldwide^{3,5}. Due to high volume of waste from SMC and BMC applications they have been the focus of much of the thermoset composite recycling effort.

A variety of technologies have been investigated for recycling SMC and BMC, but currently grinding or size reduction is the only one being employed commercially. The grinding method is simply size reduction of the waste then separation of the grindings by size. Typically impact or crushing grinding techniques such as hammer milling is used to for the size reduction steps. Impact techniques are preferred because they appear to break up the SMC without drastically reducing the length of the fibers⁶. From the impact process two general classes of recyclate are produced: fiber-length particles and filler-size particles. There is no official classification for recycled SMC size, but filler-size particles could be thought of as having average particle sizes under 0.5mm and those larger are classified as fiber-length recyclate. All of our work was done using fiber-length recyclate and will be the size we are referring to when we talk about "recyclate" unless otherwise stated.

The filler-size particles appear to substitute well for the typical mineral fillers used in molding compounds. For example when Inoh et al substituted 20 wt% 40 μm SMC recyclate particles for 24 wt% CaCO_3 filler in an SMC the tensile strength was unaffected and the flexural strength and Izod impact actually increased⁷. The only property that was always negatively affected was flexural modulus, which was reduced by less than 10%. A variety of other studies have found similar results with the little effect on strength and impact properties for filler-size recyclate substituted for CaCO_3 at low substitution amounts in SMCs⁸⁻¹⁰. Most studies did find that reductions in properties did eventually occur when high substitution amounts (up to 50 wt%) were used. Though recycled SMC and BMC of filler-size can be used in as substitution for filler in SMCs the substitution amount is limited because of viscosity increases caused by replacement of traditional fillers with recyclate^{7,10}. However successful, the limited amount of substitution possible with filler-size recyclate is not enough to close the recycling loop, also the low cost of mineral fillers limits the desire to use recycled SMC and BMC in this manner.

Another possibility and potentially more favorable use would be to use the larger recyclate components to replace virgin reinforcement or filler materials. One would hope a minimal reduction in strength would be seen when it is used to replace more expensive reinforcement and perhaps see significant improvements in strength when it is used to replace filler. There have been some investigations into the use of recyclate to replace filler and or reinforcement in BMC^{6,7,11}. Each have treated the substitution in different ways, Bledzki et al used 5, 15, and 30 wt% recyclate and kept the total glass content constant at 35 wt%⁶. Compared with the base formulation, which had a flexural strength of 129.4 Mpa, all of their BMC samples containing recyclate had lower flexural strengths. The highest strength was achieved by the BMC with 5 wt% coarse recyclate fraction replacing virgin fiber, with the flexural strength being reduced by only 7%. At greater substitution amounts flexural strength was reduced by at least 30%. Petterson and Nilsson replaced CaCO_3 with 30 wt% F1 recyclate from ERCOM^A (0.5mm and greater) to a BMC with a total of 23 wt% glass fiber⁹. They found a reduction of

^A ERCOM is a Composite Recycler in Germany

52% in the flexural strength of the BMC containing the recycle. Beldzki and Goracy used 15 and 30 wt % fiber sized recycle of different sizes in BMC to replace some fiber and some filler with total glass percentages kept at 35 wt% and total filler at 32 wt%⁸. They were the only study not to find a significant reduction in strength of the BMC with the addition of larger particles⁸. When F2 fiber sized recycle (0.5 – 1.25mm) from ERCOM was added the flexural strength was unaffected at 15 wt% substitution, but was reduced by 17% by doubling the substitution amount. Of those who performed tensile tests, they reported reductions of between 10% and 20% over their base formulations^{7,8}. In general both the tensile and flexural strength are reduced over base formulations when fiber-sized recycle is used. In all studies increasing the amount of recycle increased the reduction seen in the strength properties. Based on these results it seems reductions for BMC with recycle are much more severe than any of those seen when filler-size particles are used in SMCs. Reductions are even seen when recycle is used to replace filler in BMCs.

There has been little investigation into what causes the reduction of strength properties when recycle is used. Microscopic investigation of BMC fatigue samples containing recycle by Beldzki et al showed that cracks sometimes propagated along the borders of the recycle and the new matrix⁶. Crack propagation along the interface of the recycle and new matrix would indicate bonding between the recycle and new matrix may be weak. It has been shown that the bond between cured and new thermosets is not very strong so poor bonding would not be surprising¹². However no one has shown a definite correlation between poor bonding and reductions in strength of the BMC with recycle. In the present work the goal was to investigate the strength properties and fracture surfaces via microscopy in an attempt to identify reasons for the decrease in strength that is seen.

Experimental

Materials

To investigate the strength reduction caused when recycle is used in BMC, SMC recycle was obtained from Mecelec Composites Recyclage in France. Mecelec's SMC recycle is made by grinding SMC waste using a proprietary crushing technique. The BMC formulations used were made in-house and were based on AOC Inc.'s T766 high reactivity isophthalic based polyester resin. AOC N714 polystyrene, styrene monomer (99%), and tert-butyl peroxybenzoate (TBPB) (98%) were added to the resin. The styrene was added as the crosslinker and the TBPB as the initiator, both were used as-received from Aldrich. Zinc stearate from Aldrich was added as-received to the resin as a mold release agent. The virgin fibers used were ½ and ¼ inch Saint Gobain Vetrotex 97D(BMC) glass fibers sized for polyester and vinylester resins. Calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) from ACS International was used as filler for the BMC.

Methods

BMC Strength Samples

The BMC used in the study was made in-house. BMC containing virgin fibers, those with recycle, and those with no fiber were batched according to the formulations in Table 1. Samples containing all ½" virgin fiber, a 50/50 by weight mixture of ½" and ¼" virgin fibers, all ¼" virgin fiber, and no fiber were made to set a baseline for comparison of BMCs containing recycle and to attempt to get an estimate of what virgin fiber lengths compared well with the BMCs containing recycle. In the BMC with all recycle the virgin fiber was replaced 1 to 1 by weight with recycle. It was apparent that a 1 to 1 exchange does not have the same fiber content, but samples were formed in this manner to get an idea of how well the recycle substituted for the virgin fibers and to get a clear idea of how the recycle was behaving in the BMC.

The BMCs were made by first mixing the resin components together, followed by addition of the zinc stearate mold release. Finally, CaCO₃ and then fiber or recycle were added to the resin / mold release mixture. The compound was mixed using dough kneader blades. The compound was then

divided into 21.4 g log shaped charges approximately 100mm long and 13 mm in diameter. The charge size was selected to coincide with the 127 mm long, 13.7mm wide, and approximately 6 mm thick bars need for flexural tests¹³. The charges were cured using a compression molding setup. A steel mold clamped on a 12 ton Carver hydraulic press equipped with heated platens was used to mold the BMC. Charges were placed in the mold, which was pre-heated to 150 °C, the mold was closed and the pressure was brought to 12.8 MPa for 2 minutes. The samples were allowed to sit for three days before they were tested for strength. Before testing any roughness on the edges of the bars was smoothed using 320 grit silicon carbide sand paper.

Table 1: BMC Formulations

BMC Classification	Virgin fiber or Recyclate	No fiber
Component	Weight percent (%)	Weight percent (%)
T766	18.4	14.0
N 714	9.2	7.8
Styrene	3.1	4.3
TBPB	0.5	1.4
Zinc Stearate	1.8	2.4
CaCO ₃	50	75
Fiber or recyclate	16.7	N/A

Mechanical Testing

Flexural tests of the BMC were carried out using a COM-TEN 95 series bench top load frame equipped with a 1780 Newton (N) load cell that has a sensitivity of +/- 0.8 N. The 3 point bend tests apparatus used to test the BMC had a 100 mm span. The loading rate for the tests was 3 mm/min and failure was defined as the point at which the load decreased to 75% of the peak load. The flexural strength was determined using Equation 1 for all samples and the average of the 10 samples was calculated.

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3PL}{2bd^2} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

In Equation 1 σ_f is flexural strength and corresponds to the stress at the outer edge of the composite, P is the maximum load achieved, L is the length of the span, b is the width of the specimen, and d it the thickness of the specimen. The modulus, E_B , of the samples was determined using Equation 2.

$$E_B = \frac{L^3 m}{4bd^3} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

In Equation 2, E_B is the modulus of elasticity in bending, m is the slope of the tangent to the initial straight portion of the load-deflection curve. The value of m was determined by plotting the load deflection curve on a grid, drawing a tangent line to the initial linear portion of the curve, then finding the slope of the line.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The samples were mounted on studs, sputtered (Film-Vac Inc. Mini-Coater) using a 60% gold and 40% palladium coating. The coating for most surfaces was approximately 250Å. The scanning electron microscope used was an Amray 1810. The current was set to 20 keV, a vacuum was pulled on the sample chamber and a back-scattered mode was used. Some charging was a problem with the virgin fiber fracture surfaces as they were very jagged and the gold-pallidum coating could not reach all the recesses.

Optical Microscopy

As-received materials were analyzed using a Leitz Laborlux Optical Microscope. The crack and fracture surface were optically analyzed using an M32 Wild Heerbrugg (Switzerland) microscope with a Fiber-Lite High Intensity Illuminator (Dolan-Jenner Industries, Inc.).

Thermal Gravimetric Analysis (TGA)

The resin content of the recyclate was found using thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA). A Netzsch Jupiter STA 449C was setup with S-type TGA sample carrier with an alumina crucible for the TGA analysis. Five hundred to 1200 mg of recyclate was tested in a nitrogen atmosphere. The samples were taken from room temp to 600 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min and held at 600 for 30 minutes to ensure the resin had fully decomposed.

Acid Digestion

The samples run in TGA were placed in 3 molar HCl water solutions for approximately 1 hour to digest the CaCO₃. The samples were then rinsed with H₂O and dried in an oven. The dried samples were weighed to determine the final weight of residual fiber.

Reformulation for BMC with Recyclate

Recycled BMC was reformulated such that the amount of glass fiber added as part of the recyclate was equal to the amount of fiber in the virgin composites. The original fiber content in the virgin composites was 16.7%, however, due to fabrication difficulties, reformulated BMC with 16.7 wt% fiber from the recyclate could not be made. However, the properties of the charge were acceptable with 11.5 wt% fiber from recyclate. The formulations used for the 11.5 wt% recyclate fiber content as well as the BMC with 11.5 wt% virgin fiber content is given Table 2. Removing virgin CaCO₃ from the formulation compensated for the resin and filler added as part of the recyclate.

Table 2: Composition of 11.5 wt% Recyclate Fiber BMC and 11.5wt.% Virgin Fiber BMC

BMC Classification	11.5 wt% Virgin Fiber	11.5 wt% Fiber from Recyclate
Component	Wt%	Wt%
T 766	24.9	24.9
N 714	12.5	12.5
Styrene	4.2	4.2
Zn Stearate	2.5	2.5
TBPB	0.6	0.6
Virgin Fiber	11.5	N/A
Recyclate (53.7wt% resin, 30.4wt% fiber & 15.6 wt% filler)	N/A	38.6
CaO	1.6	1.6
CaCO ₃	42.4	15.3

Results and Discussion

The flexural properties of the BMC samples are presented in Figure 1. All the properties have been normalized to the ½” inch virgin fiber BMC as it had the highest strength. The

flexural strengths of the virgin fiber BMC decreased as the average fiber length was reduced. The BMC with recycle substituted for the virgin fibers does not achieve the strength of the virgin fiber samples with a reduction in flexural strength of 75% when compared with the 1/2" fiber. Additionally, BMC and was only 6% greater than the sample with no fiber. Since the recycle BMC has properties only slightly larger than those with no fiber it indicates that the recycle is offering very little reinforcement to the composites. Even the sample with no reinforcing fiber has a modulus that is considerably larger than that of the BMC with recycle. The same decrease in flexural modulus is seen in much of the literature, in fact the flexural modulus was the only property negatively affected in almost every study. It was even reduced when filler-sized recycle was used to replace virgin filler. Some reduction of the modulus would be expected based on the 1 to 1 substitution of recycle for fiber as the recycle likely has a lower modulus than plain fiber. Differences in the properties of the recycle and the fibers are likely the cause for some of the reduction in strength seen when the recycle is used.

Figure 1: Strength properties BMC containing all virgin materials and those with recycle. The strength properties were normalized to the 1/2" fiber BMC which had an average flexural strength of 108 MPa and a Modulus of 13.6 GPa.

The recycle used in this study had two major components, loose fiber and resin covered fiber particles. Optical micrographs of each can be seen as Figures 2 a and b. The first component, loose fibers are shown in Figure 2a, they were found to have variable amounts of resin coating, they are free of cracks, and the fibers are generally in good condition. The loose fibers had a variety of lengths, anywhere from 0.5mm up to 12.5 mm, though it is difficult to determine exact lengths and distributions due to the extreme variety in the fibers. The second component shown in Figure 2b, was resin covered fiber particles. Particles had variable shape and size as well as fiber content. The orientation of the fiber was also different for different components of the recycle. Some of the samples had very random fiber orientation and while others had large bundles of many fibers with similar alignment, however alignment

from bundle to bundle was random. The particle sizes ranged from 0.5 mm to 25mm long. The length of the fibers within the particles was not determined, as variable lengths of fiber were hidden by resin.

Figure 2a

Figure 2b

Figure 2 A & B: Optical micrographs of recycle showing the loose fiber (2a) and one of the large particles of recycle (2b).

The microscopic analysis of the recycle brought to light two issues that could affect the strength of BMC using recycle to replace virgin fiber reinforcement. For the recycle used in this study, it appeared to have an average fiber length that was shorter than even the shortest virgin fibers, which they replaced i.e. $< 1/4$ ". It is well known and has been shown from our data that shortening the fiber length will reduce the strength. If in fact the fibers in the recycle are shorter on average than the virgin fibers they are replacing, it is impossible to achieve the same strength as virgin BMC with longer fibers. One therefore needs to be careful what strength properties are being compared when recycle is used to replace fibers.

Most studies found in literature did not address the lengths of the virgin fiber versus the length of the fibers in the recycle, perhaps this is because the lengths of the fiber in the recycle are difficult to determine. Since the fiber lengths of the recycle are a function of the recycling process, it is difficult to control the size of the fibers produced and therefore the average fiber length. Because of variability in fiber length it is difficult to identify what the properties of BMC with recycle should be. Having shorter fibers, on average, likely accounts for some of the reduction in strength seen when recycle is used to substitute for fiber, but it can not explain the reductions seen when the recycle is substituted for filler, such as those seen by Petterson and Nilsson⁹.

When fiber sized recycle is used to replace filler one would expect to see some increase in strength because filler is being replaced by something with some reinforcing effect. The reinforcing effect has been seen when recycle is used to replace filler in SMC⁹. A possible explanation for the reduction of strength when larger recycle is used to replace filler in BMC is poor bonding between the recycle and the new matrix, a topic discussed later in this paper.

The second issue brought about by the microscopic analysis was that the particles contained a significant amount of resin. The large amount of resin makes a 1 to 1 substitution of recycle for virgin fiber unequal. That is, one does not add as much fiber as is removed. Bledzki et al and Bledzki and Goracy are the only two studies to date that attempted to compensate for the actual fiber content of the recycle^{6,8}. They substituted recycle for some of the fiber and filler in the BMC and kept the total glass content of the BMC constant. Making substitutions in this manner seemed to improved results with minor reductions in strength for 5 wt% recycle replacement. When 30 wt% of the BMC was recycle reductions of up to 30% from base formulations were reported, also demonstrating that fiber content is

also not the only issue at work. In an attempt to quantify how much of an effect the fiber content has on the strength values, the amount of glass fibers in our recyclate was determined. Based on the recyclate fiber content BMC with equal virgin fiber and fiber from recyclate were made.

Though it was evident that the recyclate contained a significant portion of resin it was not realized how significant it was. In fact ~54 wt% of the recyclate was resin. The exact composition of the recyclate was 53.7 wt% resin, 30.4 wt% glass fiber, and 15.6 wt% CaCO₃. With only a 30% fiber content roughly 3 times by weight recyclate would needed to be added to get equal replacement of the virgin fiber. Our original formulations had 16.7% fiber in them. Full replacement of the 16.7wt% fiber did not prove possible because the amount of recyclate needed to get enough fiber made processing virtually impossible. However, an 11.5 wt% fiber formulation was created using the recyclate. Additionally, an 11.5 wt % ¼ inch virgin fiber BMC was also made for comparison. Despite the compensation for the fiber content, the flexural strength of the BMC still was reduced by 70% compared to the 11.5 wt% virgin fiber BMC as can be seen in Table 3. Some of the reductions see in flexural strength for 11.5 wt% recyclate fiber BMC is likely due to the reduction in average fiber length from the recyclate. It is, however, difficult to determine the contribution this has because the fiber length cannot be very precisely determined. It likely does not account for all the strength reduction reported here.

Table 3: Flexural Properties of BMCs With 11.5 wt% Virgin Fiber and 11.5 wt% Fiber from Recyclate

Fiber type	11.5 wt% fiber from recyclate	11.5 wt% 1/4 inch Virgin Fiber
Flexural Strength (MPa)	23	77
Flexural Modulus (GPa)	4.0	8.2

More importantly, the 11.5 wt% recyclate fiber BMC has a flexural strength which is not statistically different^B from 1 to 1 replacement of recyclate for virgin fiber system. Since there was more than twice the amount of fiber in the 11.5 wt% virgin fiber BMC it would seem that there should have been some increase in strength over the BMC with a 1 to 1 substitution using recyclate. It should be noted that with 11.5 wt% ¼” virgin fibers we got a significant reinforcing effect compared to the no fiber system, so we are above the critical fiber volume of the composite at this composition. Based on these findings it does not appear that fiber content is the dominant cause for the reduction in the strength of BMC using recyclate to replace fiber. Further microscopic analysis of the fracture of the BMC did provide insight into the reason for the reductions in strength that are seen.

As discussed in the introduction, it is well know that an adhesive bond at the interface between two cured thermoset materials is not very strong, having as little as 60% of the strength of the bulk¹². Based on this, the bonding between the resin and fiber in the recyclate and the new resin matrix could pose a problem for BMCs containing recyclate. Since the bond between the matrix and reinforcement is what transfers the load onto the reinforcement, the interface strength is of critical importance to the integrity of the composites. Figure 3a is an SEM image of a crack in a fractured BMC sample. The crack is outlined in red, and the center of the crack is a single piece of the recyclate. It is clear that the crack in the BMC propagated around the recyclate particle not through it, as one would expect if the bond between the two were strong. If the bond were as strong as the bulk matrix, the stress would have been transferred to the recyclate with failure occurring at another origin. Since much of the glass fiber in the recyclate is contained in the particulate it is likely that those fibers are not lending as much reinforcement as it should because the load is not effectively transferred to them. Bonding was

^B Based on a 95% confidence interval two sided t test

Figure 3a

Figure 3b

Figure 3: a) An SEM micrograph of a crack in the BMC (outline in red) propagating around a piece of recycle. b) An optical image of cracks initiating at a piece of recycle, with one of them growing as part of the crack that lead to failure of the sample.

particularly a problem with the larger pieces of recycle but did not appear to be a significant problem with the loose fibers in the recycle. Behavior such as that shown in Figure 3a occurred in all the samples containing recycle. Cracks not only propagated around recycle at the surface of the BMC but also the recycle in the bulk. It was evident that the recycle at the fracture surfaces had little virgin resin sticking to it, indicating that the cracks propagated along the new matrix recycle interface. No cracks were seen at the recycle / new matrix interface when BMC sample, which had not seen any loaded were microscopically analyzed, indicating the cracks are not an artifact of processing.

Cracks propagating around the recycle particles were not the only problem with the BMC containing recycle. Often cracks in the matrix originated at the interface of the recycle particles and the new matrix as in Figure 3b. It almost appeared like the recycle was acting as defect such as a void or an impurity. Initiation of cracks at the interface of the recycle and the new matrix can also explain why even when recycle is used to replace filler, reductions in strength properties are still seen. Since the cracks are initiating at the interface as well as propagating around the recycle particles it would seem that poor bonding is cause of majority of the strength reduction. It also is likely the major reason which the BMC with 11.5 wt% fiber from recycle had such a significant reduction in strength over the 11.5 wt% virgin fiber BMC and had the same strength as the BMC with all the virgin fiber replaced with recycle. The BMC with the 11.5 wt% fibers from recycle had more recycle particles in it and therefore had more sights for initiation of cracks causing failure.

Conclusions

A variety of issues have been identified that have impact on the strength of BMC containing fiber sized recycle. Microscopic analysis of the recycle indicated that the recycle fiber lengths are shorter on average than the virgin fiber they are replacing, but no definite conclusions can be made without additional fiber size analysis. Having shorter fibers on average would make it impossible for BMC with recycle replacing virgin fiber to achieve the strength of virgin fiber BMC with longer fiber lengths. It is therefore important to keep in mind fiber lengths when strengths of base formulations and those containing recycle are being compared. The recycle also has significant amount of resin in it (~54wt%), so when it is used to directly replace virgin fiber a significant amount of reinforcement is lost. Though different recycling techniques produced recycle with different compositions the recycle used in this study had ~54 wt% resin and only ~30 wt% fiber, so almost 3 times the weight of recycle to get equal replacement of total fiber weight is needed. Even when fiber content was compensated for, a 70% reduction in flexural strength was measured, indicating that other issues were present. Investigation of

fracture surfaces revealed that the recyclate particles are not bonding well to the virgin BMC matrix. Cracks propagated around the recyclate particles and often originated at the recyclate / new matrix interface. The interface between the recyclate and the new matrix acting as crack origins might explain the strength reduction seen when recyclate is used to replace filler as well as some of the reductions seen when fiber content of the recyclate is compensated for. Though fiber length and fiber content likely have some impact on strength of the recycled BMC, there is strong evidence that poor bonding between the recyclate and the new matrix is the dominant cause of the strength reduction. Creating a stronger bond between recyclate and the new matrix is likely the first key to improving the strength of BMC with fiber-sized recyclate. Currently work is being carried out in an attempt to improve the bonding between the recyclate and the new matrix.

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